

Isentropic Compressibilities and Excess Volumes of Binary Systems of Anisole with some Aromatic Compounds Having Different Functional Groups

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Ultrasonic velocities and densities for the binary mixtures of anisole with aniline, benzonitrile, nitrobenzene and *o*-chlorophenol have been measured over the entire composition range at 308.15 K. From the experimental results, isentropic compressibilities and excess volumes of mixing are computed. The deviations in isentropic compressibility (from ideal behaviour) and excess volumes of mixing are negative for these systems at all composition. Explanations for these results have been given in terms of the interaction between their electron-donating and withdrawing groups.

THE present investigation deals with the study of intermolecular interactions of anisole with aniline, benzonitrile, nitrobenzene and *o*-chlorophenol in terms of deviations in isentropic compressibilities from ideal behaviour and volumes of mixing. Here, anisole is the electron-donating liquid. Among the other liquids, benzonitrile and nitrobenzene are electron withdrawing, while aniline and *o*-chlorophenol are hydrogen-bonded liquids.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B.D.H. except benzonitrile (S.D's) and *o*-chlorophenol (Burgoyne) and were further purified¹. Ultrasonic velocities (*u*) in liquids and liquid mixtures were measured with an ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, India) at a frequency of 2 MHz and accurate to $\pm 0.15\%$. The isentropic compressibilities (K_s) were calculated from equation (1).

$$K_s = u^{-2} \rho^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density of the liquid or liquid mixture. Excess volumes of mixing were calculated from density values of pure liquids and liquid mixtures by pycnometric method. The density values are accurate to four decimal places and excess volumes to two decimal. The temperature of the thermostat was controlled at 308.15 ± 0.01 K by means of a toluene regulator.

Results

Isentropic compressibilities: Isentropic compressibilities of the four binary systems were determined over the entire volume fraction range at 308.15 K and hence, the deviations in isentropic compressibilities (ΔK_s) based on volume fractions of the mixtures were computed from equation (2)².

$$\Delta K_s = K_s - \varphi_1 K_{s,1} - \varphi_2 K_{s,2} \quad (2)$$

where, K_s , $K_{s,1}$ and $K_{s,2}$ are the isentropic compressibilities of the mixture, component 1 and component 2, respectively, and φ_1 and φ_2 are respective volume fractions of components 1 and 2. The K_s values are accurate to $\pm 2\text{TPa}^{-1}$. The deviation of the ΔK_s value from zero indicates the extent of deviation of the mixture from ideal behaviour. The values of *u*, ρ , K_s and ΔK_s are reported in Table 1. The ΔK_s values were fitted into equation (3)³.

$$\Delta K_s = \varphi_1 \varphi_2 [A + B(\varphi_1 - \varphi_2) + C(\varphi_1 - \varphi_2)^2] \quad (3)$$

The values of the parameters A, B and C of equation (3) determined by the method of least squares are given in Table 2 along with the standard deviations $\sigma(\Delta K_s)$. The ΔK_s values of these systems are negative over the entire volume fraction range.

Excess volumes of mixing: Excess volumes of mixing (V^E) were determined at 308.15 K for these systems over the entire mole fraction range and are recorded in Table 3. Excess volumes were fitted into the analytical equation of the type (4)⁴.

$$V^E = x_1 x_2 [A + B(x_1 - x_2) + C(x_1 - x_2)^2] \quad (4)$$

where, x_1 and x_2 are mole fractions of components 1 and 2, respectively. The values of A, B and C of equation (4) were determined by the method of least-squares and are recorded in Table 4 along with the standard deviations $\sigma(V^E)$. The V^E values are negative for these systems over the entire mole fraction range.

Discussion

Anisole is an electron-donor because of the two lone pairs of electrons of its oxygen atom^{5,6}. The difference in molar volumes of unlike components is not large in these systems except that of anisole and aniline.

TABLE 1—ISENTROPIC COMPRESSIBILITIES OF BINARY SYSTEMS CONTAINING ANISOLE

Temp. = 308.15 K

Volume fraction of (1), φ_1	ρ g cm ⁻³	u m sec ⁻¹	K_s TPa ⁻¹	ΔK_s TPa ⁻¹
Anisole (1) + Aniline (2)				
0	1.0092	1601	386.6	0
0.1754	1.0042	1560	409.2	-5.1
0.3381	0.9996	1522	431.9	-8.1
0.4982	0.9949	1485	454.6	-9.5
0.6430	0.9906	1451	479.5	-8.7
0.7817	0.9865	1419	503.4	-6.7
0.9153	0.9824	1389	527.6	-3.6
1.0000	0.9798	1369	544.6	0
Anisole (1) + Benzotrile (2)				
0	0.9918	1385	525.6	0
0.1559	0.9904	1384	527.1	-1.5
0.3100	0.9889	1382	529.5	-2.0
0.4652	0.9872	1381	531.1	-3.3
0.6108	0.9855	1379	533.6	-3.6
0.7562	0.9837	1376	536.9	-3.0
0.9018	0.9815	1373	540.5	-2.2
1.0000	0.9798	1369	544.6	0
Anisole (1) + Nitrobenzene (2)				
0	1.1886	1423	415.5	0
0.1600	1.1560	1416	431.4	-4.7
0.3134	1.1244	1408	448.6	-7.6
0.4625	1.0934	1400	466.6	-8.6
0.6111	1.0624	1390	487.2	-7.2
0.7746	1.0277	1380	510.9	-4.6
0.9033	1.0005	1373	530.2	-1.9
1.0000	0.9798	1369	544.6	0
Anisole (1) + <i>o</i> -Chlorophenol (2)				
0	1.2287	1381	426.7	0
0.1549	1.1914	1380	440.7	-4.3
0.3100	1.1535	1379	455.9	-7.3
0.4619	1.1159	1378	471.9	-9.3
0.6051	1.0802	1377	488.2	-9.8
0.7586	1.0414	1375	507.9	-8.2
0.9001	1.0054	1372	528.4	-4.4
1.0000	0.9798	1369	544.6	0

TABLE 2—VALUES OF PARAMETERS A, B AND C OF EQUATION (3) AND OF STANDARD DEVIATIONS $\sigma(\Delta K_s)$ OF BINARY SYSTEMS

Temp. = 308.15 K

Binary mixture of anisole with	A TPa ⁻¹	B TPa ⁻¹	C TPa ⁻¹	$\sigma(\Delta K_s)$ TPa ⁻¹
Aniline	-37.2	-5.5	-2.7	0.3
Benzotrile	-12.3	-7.6	-8.7	0.3
Nitrobenzene	-33.3	8.3	8.0	0.2
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	-38.1	-10.7	-3.7	0.1

In the anisole-aniline system, the change in thermodynamic properties on mixing may be due to the following factors apart from the size difference: (i) breaking up of the hydrogen bonds in aniline by the addition of anisole and (ii) interaction between unlike molecules. The negative values of ΔK_s and V^E suggest that the latter factor is the predominant one. This interaction may be due to

TABLE 3—EXCESS VOLUMES OF BINARY SYSTEMS

Temp. = 308.15 K

Mole fraction of (1), x_1	Density g cm ⁻³	Excess volume cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Anisole (1) + Aniline (2)		
0	1.0092	0
0.0810	1.0065	-0.010
0.1510	1.0043	-0.015
0.2203	1.0020	-0.022
0.2993	0.9996	-0.033
0.4536	0.9949	-0.035
0.5199	0.9930	-0.040
0.6009	0.9906	-0.032
0.7496	0.9865	-0.030
0.9004	0.9824	-0.012
1.0000	0.9798	0
Anisole (1) + Benzotrile (2)		
0	0.9918	0
0.0961	0.9908	-0.023
0.1957	0.9899	-0.060
0.2978	0.9889	-0.088
0.3940	0.9878	-0.097
0.4954	0.9866	-0.100
0.6015	0.9854	-0.108
0.7006	0.9842	-0.105
0.7863	0.9830	-0.084
0.9053	0.9814	-0.059
1.0000	0.9798	0
Anisole (1) + Nitrobenzene (2)		
0	1.1886	0
0.0804	1.1713	-0.043
0.1515	1.1560	-0.070
0.2180	1.1419	-0.099
0.2997	1.1244	-0.112
0.4465	1.0934	-0.129
0.5157	1.0790	-0.138
0.5957	1.0624	-0.138
0.7635	1.0277	-0.093
0.8973	1.0005	-0.049
1.0000	0.9798	0
Anisole (1) + <i>o</i> -Chlorophenol (2)		
0	1.2287	0
0.0809	1.2081	-0.048
0.1480	1.1914	-0.110
0.2112	1.1755	-0.145
0.2987	1.1535	-0.180
0.4487	1.1159	-0.209
0.5120	1.1001	-0.210
0.5923	1.0802	-0.211
0.7487	1.0414	-0.159
0.8952	1.0054	-0.080
1.0000	0.9798	0

TABLE 4—VALUES OF PARAMETERS A, B AND C OF EQUATION (4) AND OF STANDARD DEVIATIONS $\sigma(V^E)$ OF BINARY SYSTEMS

Temp. = 308.15 K

Binary mixture of anisole with	A cm ³ mol ⁻¹	B cm ³ mol ⁻¹	C cm ³ mol ⁻¹	$\sigma(V^E)$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Aniline	-0.1491	-0.0079	0.0263	0.003
Benzotrile	-0.4247	-0.1886	-0.0824	0.007
Nitrobenzene	-0.5428	0.0235	-0.0092	0.005
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	-0.8753	-0.0378	0.1265	0.008

the formation of hydrogen bond between oxygen of anisole and hydrogen atom of the amino group in aniline. Such interaction was reported for *o*-chloro-aniline-dioxane system⁷.

The negative values of ΔK , and V^E of anisole-benzonitrile system may be due to complexation between unlike molecules through charge-transfer interactions. Anisole acts as an electron-donor and benzonitrile as an electron-acceptor. This is in accordance with the view of Bolinga *et al.*⁸, that specific interaction of the type $-C\equiv N \cdots O <$ may be responsible for negative excess volume. Similar interaction was observed by Suri and Chawla⁹ for nitrile-ether binary system.

Nitrobenzene is an electron acceptor. Therefore, it is expected that in a solution with an electron-donating substance, it will form a charge-transfer complex¹⁰. The negative ΔK , and V^E values of anisole-nitrobenzene system is due to this electron donor-acceptor interaction between unlike molecules.

In anisole-*o*-chlorophenol system, the change in thermodynamic properties may be due to (i) the breaking up of both inter- and intra-molecular hydrogen bonds in *o*-chlorophenol by the addition of anisole and (ii) the formation of hydrogen bonds between unlike molecules⁷. The negative values of ΔK , and V^E of this system show that the latter effect contributes more to the change in thermodynamic properties on mixing. In *o*-chlorophenol, the inductive effect (electron-withdrawing) of chlorine atom is greater than its mesomeric effect (electron-donating)¹¹. Hence, the hydroxyl group

in *o*-chlorophenol is highly polarised. Consequently, the hydrogen bonding between monomers of *o*-chlorophenol and anisole will be strong. Infrared studies^{12,13} also support the formation of hydrogen bonds between phenols and electron-donors.

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